

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

***BULLETIN OF* FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

2025, №6 (20)

МИНИСТЕРСТВО ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ
РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН

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ТИББИЁТ АХБОРОТНОМАСИ
ВЕСТНИК ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОЙ И
КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

Научный журнал по фундаментальным и клиническим
проблемам медицины
основан в 2022 году

Бухарским государственным медицинским институтом
имени Абу Али ибн Сино
выходит один раз в 2 месяца

Главный редактор – Ш.Ж. ТЕШАЕВ

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2025, № 6 (20)

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О журнале

Журнал зарегистрирован
в Управлении печати и информации
Бухарской области
№ 1640 от 28 мая 2022 года.

Журнал внесен в список
утвержденный приказом № 370/б
от 8 мая 2025 года реестром ВАК
в раздел медицинских наук.

Отпечатано в типографии ООО
“Шарк-Бухоро”. г. Бухара,
ул. Ўзбекистон Муस्ताкиллиги, 70/2.

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THE COMBINATION OF THE COLLAGEN OSTEOGENIC MATERIAL "OSTEON 3" WITH A PATIENT'S BLOOD PLASMA IN INDIVIDUALS WITH CHRONIC PERIODONTITIS**Usmanov R.F.**

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Resume. *These studies suggest that changes in osteon structure and bone microstructure are sensitive to metabolic and physiological conditions, but do not address the effects of combining "OSTEON 3" with blood plasma for chronic periodontitis. The basis of the research was the results of clinical examination and observation of 40 patients with destructive forms of chronic periodontitis with different localization (single-rooted or multi-rooted teeth) and different age groups (18-50 years old). Patients with traditional method of treatment (using calcium hydroxide)-15 patients. Treatment with the use of bone-plastic material -(25 patients). Finding and creating novel materials and techniques to cure harmful types of periodontitis is the aim of this project. The study group exhibited a substantial increase in bone tissue regeneration and restoration, as evidenced by a 96.2% decrease in adverse treatment outcomes and a 57% increase in bone density in comparison to the conventional method. The application of bone-plastic materials, introduced via the tooth's root canal into the periapical destruction area, results in a statistically significant enhancement in the clinical efficacy of bone tissue restoration surrounding the tooth apex compared to treatment methods that do not utilize reparative osteogenesis optimisation.*

Keywords: *advanced materials, platelet-rich fibrin, hydroxyapatite, NovaBone, biological agents, directed tissue regeneration, Osteon 3 collagen, chronic periodontitis.*

СУРУНКАЛИ ПАРОДОНТИТИ БОР ШАХСЛАРДА КОЛЛАГЕНЛИ ОСТЕОГЕН МАТЕРИАЛ "ОСТЕОН 3"НИ БЕМОРНИНГ ҚОН ПЛАЗМАСИ БИЛАН КОМБИНАЦИЯСИ**Усманов Р.Ф.**

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Резюме: *Ушбу тадқиқотлар остеон тузилишидаги ва суяк микротузилишидаги ўзгаришлар метаболик ва физиологик шароитларга сезгир эканлигини кўрсатади, лекин сурункали пародонтитда "ОСТЕОН 3" ни қон плазмаси билан комбинациялаш самарадорлигини тўлиқ ёритиб бермайди. Тадқиқотга асос қилиб, турли локализацияга эга (якка илдизли ёки кўп илдизли тишлар) ва турли ёш гуруҳларига (18-50 ёш) мансуб сурункали пародонтитнинг деструктив шакллари билан касалланган 40 нафар беморнинг клиник текширув ва кузатув натижалари олинди. Анъанавий даволаш усули (кальций гидроксиди ёрдамида) қўлланилган беморлар — 15 киши. Суяк-пластик материалдан фойдаланиб даволанганлар — 25 бемор. Ушбу лойиҳанинг мақсади — пародонтитнинг деструктив турларини даволаш учун янги материаллар ва усулларни излаш ва яратишидир. Тадқиқот гуруҳида суяк тўқимасининг регенерацияси ва тикланиши сезиларли даражада ошган, бу анъанавий усулга нисбатан ножўя даволаш натижаларининг 96,2% га камайиши ва суяк зичлигининг 57% га ошиши билан тасдиқланди. Суяк-пластик материалларнинг тиш илдиз канали орқали периопекал деструкция соҳасига киритилиши репаратив остеогенезни оптималлаштиришни қўлламайдиган даволаш усулларига нисбатан, тиш учи атрофидаги суяк тўқимасини тиклашнинг клиник самарадорлигини статистик жиҳатдан аҳамиятли даражада оширишга олиб келади.*

Калит сўзлар: *замонавий материаллар, тромбоцитларга бой фибрин, гидроксипатит, NovaBone, биологик агентлар, йўналтирилган тўқима регенерацияси, Osteon 3 коллагени, сурункали пародонтит.*

КОМБИНАЦИЯ КОЛЛАГЕНОВОГО ОСТЕОГЕННОГО МАТЕРИАЛА "ОСТЕОН 3" С ПЛАЗМОЙ КРОВИ ПАЦИЕНТА У ЛИЦ С ХРОНИЧЕСКИМ ПАРОДОНТИТОМ**Усманов Р.Ф.**

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Резюме. *Данные исследования предполагают, что изменения в структуре остеонов и микро-структуре кости чувствительны к метаболическим и физиологическим условиям, но не рассматривают эффекты комбинирования "ОСТЕОН 3" с плазмой крови при хроническом пародонтите. Основой исследования послужили результаты клинического обследования и наблюдения 40 пациентов с деструктивными формами хронического пародонтита различной локализации (однокорневые или*

многокорневые зубы) и разных возрастных групп (18-50 лет). Пациенты с традиционным методом лечения (с использованием гидроксида кальция) — 15 человек. Лечение с использованием костно-пластического материала — 25 пациентов. Целью данного проекта является поиск и создание новых материалов и методик для лечения деструктивных видов пародонтита. В исследуемой группе наблюдалось существенное увеличение регенерации и восстановления костной ткани, о чем свидетельствует снижение неблагоприятных исходов лечения на 96,2% и увеличение плотности костной ткани на 57% по сравнению с традиционным методом. Применение костно-пластических материалов, введенных через корневой канал зуба в область периапикальной деструкции, приводит к статистически значимому повышению клинической эффективности восстановления костной ткани вокруг верхушки зуба по сравнению с методами лечения, которые не используют оптимизацию репаративного остеогенеза.

Ключевые слова: современные материалы, фибрин, обогащенный тромбоцитами (плазмой), гидроксипатит, NovaBone, биологические агенты, направленная тканевая регенерация, коллаген "Остеон 3", хронический пародонтит.

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Introduction. The pathomorphologic state of periapical tissues and the level of nonspecific resistance of the patient's organism are the chief determinants of the probability of the development of complications, the nature of clinical manifestations, and the outcome of chronic periodontitis [17,18]. A high percentage of complications have been identified following treatment of this condition. The question concerning the repair of the structure and function of periapical tissues throughout time remains pressing [19,20].

The management of periapical foci of inflammation remains an unresolved issue in medicine. This is particularly relevant in light of the potential for periapical utilisation of methods to affect the progression of reparative osteogenesis [21, 22]. The identification and development of such materials are the primary focus of the research of a variety of specialities, including dental surgeons, therapists, periodontists, traumatologists, and orthopaedists. Although there are several methods for optimising osteogenesis, a review of the literature and common practice reveals that each one has certain disadvantages and that there is no clear consensus regarding how successful they are [22, 23, 24].

According to the aforementioned, the research that is intended to identify, search for, develop, and justify the use of osteoplastic means for the treatment of destructive forms of periodontitis remains pertinent in both theoretical and practical terms [25,26]. Significant attention has been paid to the optimisation of treatment for chronic periodontitis, particularly through the use of bone-plastic materials, in recent years. In order to improve clinical outcomes for patients with this condition, numerous studies have investigated various approaches and materials. [27,28,29] A systematic review of full-mouth treatment concepts for chronic periodontitis was conducted by some works, emphasising the significance of comprehensive approaches in managing the disease. This review emphasises the importance of incorporating a variety of treatment modalities, such as the use of bone-plastic materials, to obtain the best possible results [2,30].

In the context of intraosseous periodontal defects, the clinical efficacy of NovaBone [4], a bioactive glass-based augmentation material, was assessed in a pilot study. The study demonstrated substantial enhancements in clinical parameters, including pocket depth and attachment loss, as a result of surgical augmentation, indicating that innovative bone-plastic materials can be instrumental in regenerative periodontal therapy. Additionally, the efficiency of the osteoplastic material "Osteon 3 collagen"® was evaluated through computer tomography, further supporting the use of advanced materials. This study elucidated the material's efficacy in facilitating healing and regeneration in periodontal therapies, demonstrating a favourable response to tooth root reactions.

A study has also been conducted on the combination of hydroxyapatite grafts and platelet-rich fibrin (PRF). The application of PRF alongside porous hydroxyapatite markedly enhanced clinical and radiographic results in the management of three-wall intrabony defects in individuals with chronic periodontitis [7]. The potential of combining biological and synthetic materials in periodontal regeneration was further highlighted by [9], who reported a significant increase in bone fill percentages when comparing PRF combined with hydroxyapatite to controls. studied a complex treatment approach that included biocomposite materials and guided tissue regeneration (GTR) in addition to osteoplastic materials [8]. Their results suggested that the interdisciplinary approach, which involved the use of autogenous growth factors, was effective in managing chronic generalised periodontitis. This reinforces the notion that the combination of multiple treatment strategies can improve patient outcomes.

Lastly, the ongoing necessity for innovative treatment algorithms and medications to stabilise chronic periodontitis was emphasized[10]. The literature shows increasing agreement on the efficacy of using bone-plastic materials and novel treatment strategies in the management of chronic periodontitis. Their study assessed a comprehensive treatment regimen that included novel agents, indicating that the integration of advanced materials and techniques is essential for prolonging remission and improving the overall management of chronic periodontitis. It appears that the integration of these materials with biological agents and comprehensive treatment approaches improves clinical outcomes, necessitating additional research and implementation in clinical application.

Method and materials. Results from clinical examinations and observations of 40 patients with destructive forms of chronic periodontitis in various age groups (18–50 years old) and localisations (single- or multi-rooted teeth) served as the foundation for the dissertation. Fifteen individuals received therapy using the standard method of calcium hydroxide. Treatment utilising bone-plastic material - (25 patients) The treatment outcomes in the groups were assessed based on three qualitative characteristics.

A satisfactory one	Pathologic alterations in the oral mucosa and the cause of tooth decay in the absence of complaints
adequate	- in the event that the causative tooth changes, causing positive dental percussion and/or a mild biting pain complaint
inadequate	The existence of complaints alongside objective indicators or a mixture of objective indicators

In group 1, the treatment was conducted using the traditional method without post-apical intervention. The Crown-down technique involved the mechanical cleaning and enlargement of the root canal.

The study group, consisting of 25 individuals (40 teeth), utilised the bone-plastic substance “Osteon 3 collagen” and included cases of exacerbated chronic periodontitis (10), granulomatous form (12), and granulomatous form (18).

The control group utilising hydroxydocalcium-based paste comprised 15 individuals (30 teeth), exhibiting worsening of chronic periodontitis in 10 cases, granulomatous form in 9 cases, and granulomatous form in 11 cases.

Endodontic treatment technique for destructive periodontitis with bone grafting materials. Following the primary and supplementary research methodologies, we commenced conservative treatment for chronic periodontitis.

Use of the bone-plastic preparation "Osteon 3 Collagen" in conjunction with autoplasm in clinical settings. We investigated and executed intricate dental treatments on 25 individuals aged 25 to 50 years diagnosed with "chronic destructive periodontitis."

Results of the research. Before to and following treatment, as well as three and six months later, all patients had clinical and radiologic examinations of their teeth.

The parameters and character of bone structure recovery after treatment, as well as the degree of bone resorption before treatment, were considered.

The status of periapical dental tissues was assessed with the PMA index.

Iodinol was utilised to maintain canal hygiene.

Mechanical instrumentation of root canals and supra-apical lesions was conducted.

Using an endodontic needle with a 0.1 mm diameter, autoplasm enriched with platelets was injected intracanal. The apex's physiological narrowing was stretched to 35 size (threads-files of 0.4 taper) in accordance with the ISO scale. The amount of autoplasm injected was between 0.1 and 0.4 ml. Depending on the extent of the destruction, after 3 minutes, the bone-plastic preparation “Osteon 3 collagen” was injected apically with a canal filler, in quantities ranging from 0.1 to 0.4 mg. The canal was subsequently dried, and permanent obturation was executed using Adseal sealer and gutta-percha, followed by hermetic closure of the cavity.

The endodontic treatment of chronic periodontitis was generally conducted in the control and study groups of patients in accordance with the generally accepted scheme. This method involved the use of standardised instrumental, pharmacological, and physiotherapeutic methods to treat the root canal and pericardial tissues. The primary distinction in the treatment of the investigated group was the final phase of the treatment, which was conducted in accordance with the study's methodology. Prior to the final filling of the root canal, the perchannel bone-plastic material was omitted in conjunction with autoplasm to optimise reparative osteogenesis in the area of periapical bone destruction.

In all patients, both in the experimental and control groups, conventional endodontic treatment was conducted during the initial visit. Anaesthesia was administered, the carious cavity was prepared, the tooth cavity was accessed using diamond turbine burs, and the root canals were accessed and widened. Fractional evacuation of pulp necrosis was performed, along with instrumental treatment of the root canal under apex locator guidance, utilising endodontic instruments such as K-files and H-files, as well as medications including antiseptics, nitrofurazone preparations, and a 3% sodium hypochlorite solution. Physiotherapeutic treatment was also implemented.

After 5-7 days, we removed the temporary filling and root medicament dressing, and conducted further instrumental therapy with endodontic instruments (rimers, H-files) ranging from #10-40, monitored by an apex finder. Subsequently, the root canal was subjected to pharmacological treatment with the aforementioned preparations and the apical focus. The canal was subsequently dried and filled with a medicament dressing containing calcium oxide or hydroxide preparations, as well as iodoform, as illustrated by the materials "Vitapex," "Metapex," and "Metapex."

The allocation for transcanal application was chosen with a level of pulverisation such that the particle size was half that of the root canal lumen.

Then, progressive movements were employed to atraumatically retract the canal filler (Lentulo) into the focal point of periapical inflammation. The volume of the extracted material is contingent upon the diameter of the destruction focal point.

The clinical evaluation of the quality and efficiency of the developed methods of endodontic treatment of teeth was conducted in the following terms: 1, 7, and 14 days, based on patients' complaints and clinical, standard methods of examination. The quality of endodontic procedures, the state of periapical tooth tissues, and the results of endodontic treatment were evaluated radiologically using a visigraph and conventional imaging methods. A radiological and clinical assessment of the outcomes of endodontic treatment for teeth was conducted at six months, one year, and three years post-treatment.

Patients with chronic periodontitis are presented as clinical cases to exemplify the treatment methodologies described.

Clinical cases of patients with chronic periodontitis are provided as a visual representation of the outlined treatment methodologies.

Dental patient medical record. Patient D., aged 46, reported intermittent pain in the 23rd tooth and challenges with mastication.

The 23rd tooth had been previously treated for deep caries; however, the filling dislodged, and she has not received any further treatment for over six months. She has no facial asymmetry, lymph nodes are not enlarged, palpation is harmless, and there is no fistula on the facial skin. Additionally, her mouth opening is not compromised.

Objectively, the 23rd tooth has a deep carious cavity formed by necrotic dentin. The tooth cavity is painless to probe, but percussion is excruciating. The EOM is 160 μ A, and palpation along the transitional fold is painless. The mucous membrane is devoid of features, and the tooth is mobile of the 1st degree.

The radiograph of the 23rd tooth reveals a focal area of bone tissue degradation at the tooth apex, characterised by a round shape, with the surrounding spongy substance exhibiting increased density.

The diagnosis established, based on the acquired data, is chronic granulomatous periodontitis of the 23rd tooth.

The patient was treated using the developed approach, which involved using autoplasm and bone-plastic preparation apically. The radiologic pictures pertaining to this case are presented below (Fig. 1).

Dental patient's medical record.

Patient G., aged 30, reported experiencing pain upon occlusion with tooth 47.

Previously, 47 teeth were extracted for orthopaedic purposes. Objectively: Gingival mucosa is pale pink in colour, percussion and probing are innocuous, and there are 47 teeth under the crown. Investigation of root canals indicated the inadequacy of root fillings.

Radiologically, the periodontal gap has expanded in the region of the root ends 47, resulting in a rounded bone destruction foci in both roots (Fig. 2).

A comparative examination of the outcomes of dental treatment using the developed methods and the results of classical methods.

To assess the short-term outcomes of treatment for patients with chronic periodontitis during a timeframe of 6 to 12 months.

Following the placement of root canal fillings. Initially, the frequency and characteristics of treatment complications during this control period are considered: the emergence of pain, oedema in the transition layer, dental pain, objective assessments, and pain upon percussion.

Figure 1. Radiograph of patient D., aged 46, dental medical record No. 3467. Chronic apical periodontitis affecting 23 teeth. In the phase of endodontic therapy for 23 teeth. The canals were filled with "Adseal" substance and gutta-percha posts. Following the excision of osseous tissue in the region of periapical damage (during treatment and after a three-month interval).

Fig. 2. Radiograph of patient G., aged 30 years. Chronic granulomatous periodontitis affecting tooth 47. The outcome of endodontic therapy employing bone-plastic material in conjunction with autoplasm.

During the initial two weeks following the completion of root canals, 11 patients in the control group reported experiencing pain during biting, while four additional patients (23.3%) reported pain during percussion. Complications were not observed in 15 patients (41.7%).

The group under investigation did not exhibit any complications in the form of odontogenic inflammatory processes. However, 20 patients (%) reported discomfort when occluding on the treated tooth, which self-resolved within 3-5 days without necessitating further therapeutic intervention.

Before and after treatment, radiologic examinations were conducted to assess the extent of bone resorption. Instrumental management of root canals, anaesthetic intervention, and apical focused therapy, expansion of physiological constrictions up to 30 orders of magnitude on the ISO scale, and intracranial autologous platelet-rich injection utilising an endodontic needle with a 0.1 mm diameter.

Autologous plasma for injection: 0.1 to 0.2 millilitres. After 3 minutes, 0.1-0.2 mg of Osteon and 0.1-0.2 mg of collagen were injected apically utilising canal fillers.

Subsequently, they were desiccated, thoroughly cleansed, and the procedure was concluded. Therefore, the radiologic data analysis validated the effectiveness of Collagen Osteogenic Osteon 3, which caused bone treated with apical injections enriched with autologous platelet-rich platelets (PRP) to resorb.

The clinical imaging data analysis confirmed the feasibility of post-apical injection therapy with platelet-rich autologous platelet-rich factor (PRF) in combination with osteoplastic collagen preparations Osteon 3 collagen, which are already enhancing results in the early phases of therapy. As a result of meticulous cleaning of the root canal, apical region, and enhancement of the bone regeneration process, bone density increased by 57% relative to the conventional method: in the control group, bone tissue in the periapical area was fully and partially restored, while in the study group, 13 teeth ($40.8 \pm 1.4\%$) and 30 teeth ($97.2 \pm 1.1\%$) were observed to be completely and partially restored, respectively.

Conservative treatment of chronic periodontitis is considered to have an unfavourable prognosis when foci of destruction of periapical bone tissue do not regenerate completely or partially one year following root canal filling. The incidence of negative treatment outcomes in the control group was 59.2%. The occurrence of negative outcomes in the therapy group was 2.8%. The principal clinical efficacy rates derived from it were presented with 95% confidence intervals: absolute risk reduction (ARR) = 56.4% and relative risk reduction (RRR) = 96.8%.

Clinical efficacy indicators of bone grafting materials in treating patients with destructive chronic periodontitis.

Periapical bone regeneration was absent in the control group, resulting in 4 (2.8%) negative treatment outcomes in contrast to 90 (59.2%) in the control group.

The method we devised for the treatment of patients with chronic periodontitis using osteogenic materials can be reliably evaluated using the statistical analysis parameters. Consequently, the principal indices of treatment efficacy derived from our investigation were juxtaposed with the reference values.

According to the definition, the risk reduction index value of 86.8% derived in this statistical analysis falls within the category of values that "always corresponds to a clinically significant effect." The same is true for the extent of the disparity. The prevalence of negative treatment effects in the control group was 63.2%. The occurrence of adverse events in the therapy group was 2.8%.

The intricate examination of the dynamics of radiologic changes in the focus of destruction, which serves as an objective indicator of the efficacy of periodontal treatment, is more challenging.

Employing a combination of collagen Osteon 3 and autoblood, we observed an additional anomaly in the radiologic alterations of post-apical tissue regeneration, the resolution of which is contingent upon the selected material for post-apical intervention.

The regeneration of bone tissue is observed to be enhanced throughout the entire length of the focus of devastation when a combination of the preparation "Osteon 3 collagen" and autoplasmic blood is employed. - in the periphery of the rarefaction centre (the region of destruction diminishes and the level of lucency declines after two months).

The extent of bone tissue regeneration in the control group of patients as observed in radiography.

Detailed comparison of results in groups and follow-up investigation one year after treatment

Control group: complete tissue recovery rate of $10.5 \pm 7.1\%$, partial bone recovery rate of $30.0 \pm 10.1\%$, and $47.4 \pm 11.5\%$ in the event of undiagnosed bone destruction and haemorrhage as indicated by pathology. 11 augmented by 4%;

Implantation (utilising the same bone group): complete bone tissue restoration ($87.0 \pm 8.6\%$), partial bone tissue restoration ($10.1 \pm 6.4\%$), and focal tissue injury ($2.9 \pm 1.2\%$).

In patients with chronic periodontitis, the clinical efficacy of optimising reparative osteogenesis in the periapical bone degradation focus using the collagen osteogenic material "Osteon-3" was statistically significant.

The greatest clinical efficacy for bone tissue regeneration was exhibited by produced autologous and $95.0 \pm 8.8\%$ Osteon 3 collagen.

As a result, the quantitative assessment of patients with destructive periodontitis who received trans-apical injections revealed that the severity of destruction of apical periodontal tissue in the control group was between 1 and 2 points, the integrity of bone tissue in this area was not compromised, and the size of the focus of destruction was no more than 1 mm. The use of a combination of the preparation mixture of "Osteon 3 collagen" and autologous blood plasma yielded the most promising results. In the primary group - 0 points, indicating the absence of pathological abnormalities on the radiograph.

In the long-term (1.5 years) following root canal therapy, clinical efficacy in the primary group of patients was superior to that in the control group. Therefore, the control group had 15 teeth (72.3%±4.2%) and the main group had 40 teeth (99.3%±0.6%) that had received complete peripheral bone tissue restoration. The standard form of irritation of the alveolar process was observed during the clinical-instrumental examination of the teeth. The teeth were bruised, the patient did not have any complaints, and there was no pathologic displacement of the teeth.

Statistical analysis parameters enable us to accurately assess the method we have developed for the treatment of chronic periodontitis patients with long-lived osteogenic materials. Consequently, the comparison was made between the primary indices of treatment efficacy that were obtained in our study and the reference values. The risk reduction index value derived from this statistical analysis (96.2%) aligns with the category "always corresponds to a clinically significant effect" as defined.

The odds ratio index value corroborates this finding. The occurrence of negative treatment outcomes in the control group was 20.1%. The incidence of adverse events in the therapy group was 0.7%.

Parameters indicating the risk of adverse treatment outcomes were computed and presented with a 95% confidence interval. The absolute risk reduction is 40.1% for ATS. Relative risk, Odds Ratio = 95%. Relative risk decrease, SOR = 90.1%. The odds ratio was 0.08.

The clinical efficacy of various bone grafting materials was compared, and it was found that there is no statistical difference between them for bone restoration around the apex of the tooth in patients who have undergone treatment for chronic periodontitis. However, the combination of these two materials is significantly more effective than either material alone.

Conclusion. Consequently, the clinical efficacy of bone tissue restoration around the apex of the tooth is statistically significantly enhanced by the use of bone-plastic materials that are introduced through the root canal of the tooth and into the area of periapical destruction, as opposed to treatment methods that do not incorporate reparative osteogenesis optimisation. The optimal treatment outcomes are attained through the utilisation of a mixture of finely fragmented demineralised lyophilised spongy allostium and the preparation "Osteon 3 collagen" (synthetic 3-tricalcium phosphate).

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For citation: Usmanov R.F. The combination of the collagen osteogenic material "OSTEON 3" with a patient's blood plasma in individuals with chronic periodontitis // *Bulletin of Fundamental and Clinic Medicine*. – 2025. – № 6(20). – P. 294–301. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17657778>